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Analysis of superbolides over the last 2000 years in an important year for planetary defense

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This study embarks on a journey through time with superbolides events. Researchers and students from the UCM have compiled a database built on international newspapers; this repository holds a thousand events, detailing their potential damages. In parallel, the detection methods have been refined by utilizing radiometers, infrasound sensors and seismic networks. The abundance of such records in February caught the interest of astronomers. Noteworthy events are Chelyabinsk (February 15, 2013) and a recent asteroid entry over the English Channel (February 13, 2023). This study merges two databases to analyze the underlying patterns of superbolide occurrences, considering the amplified flux resulting from meteor showers.

1 Introduction

The article delves into superbolide events, characterized by their unusual brightness, with no fixed magnitude threshold but typically referred to as those shining brighter than the Moon (magnitude less than -13). Researchers from the University Complutense of Madrid have compiled a database spanning from 419 AD (Greg, 1860), sourced from digitized news articles from national and international newspapers, despite inherent observational biases. The database contains rich information on over 1203 events with descriptions of damages, magnitudes, sizes, and related events. They are filtered because of the data volume concentration.

Today, superbolide detection involves various methods, including radiometers, infrasound sensors, luminous sensor satellites, and seismic stations worldwide. To comprehensively analyze the frequency of these events annually, researchers have added a second, more recent database from NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory, covering the past 35 years.

The study aims to show an unexpected abundance of superbolides on atypical dates, not accounted for by annual meteor showers, which usually boost their frequency. The focus on bolide records in February, particularly from Feb 7 to Feb 22 (Denning, 1922), has piqued astronomers' interest due to unique detonations (Denning, 1879). Notably, the Chelyabinsk event on February 15, 2013, and similar occurrences, like the South African bolide on February 1, 1994, have gained fame (Emel'yanenko et al., 2013).

Recently, in early February, there were days with multiple events in Spain, including a daytime bolide on February 5¹ and an asteroid impact over the English Channel on February 13, 2023, predicted 7 hours prior by Krisztián Sárneczky².

An extensive non-parametric and Bayesian statistical analysis, using Kernel Density Estimation and the Bayes' Theorem, is performed to approximate the probability density functions of both databases.

2 Non-parametric and Bayesian analysis of events

The data follows an unknown statistical distribution, making non-parametric and Bayesian approaches, particularly Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), the most reliable method. KDE aims to transform the unknown data distribution into a known one suitable for applying classical parametric statistical methods. This method treats each observation as a distribution, expanding on the histogram concept, where each contributes to the increase in probability density in its vicinity. Hence, the kernel, the function determining the distribution of each observation's effect, plays a crucial role in estimating the overall density function. While a Gaussian kernel is commonly used, other options such as exponential, linear, and cosine kernels are available³ (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Observations as normal distributions, KDE, Gaussian kernel

the-channel/

³<https://statstinking21.github.io/>

statstinking21-python/10-BayesianStatistics.html

¹<http://www.spmn.uji.es/ESP/SPMNlist.html>

²<https://www.imo.net/imminent-asteroid-entry-over->

The final step to obtain the distribution of the entire set of observations, the sample, is to sum each distribution, resulting in the estimated distribution of the sample in blue (Figure 2), then each observation contributes smoothly. This treatment is well-suited to our study, especially with a Gaussian kernel, as both the dating of events and the events themselves can conform better to distributions rather than exact positions. This is due to the uncertainty in dating; for instance, in the first dataset treated, most events are dated with a date only, without specifying the time, and in cases where the time is specified, there is an uncertainty ranging from 3 to 6 hours. Additionally, an event may be related to one of its consecutive events and vice-versa.

Figure 2 – Final estimated distribution from a random dataset

2.1 From 2000 years to 200: first sample

Describing the first sample, the data belong to a database collected previously (Zamora et al., 2015). The database consists of events dating from the 5. century AD to 2014, reported in newspapers such as the New York Times and the National Library of Spain’s newspaper archive, among others. The intention was to truly collect those superbolide events, and if an event was memorable enough to have current news about it, it is because they were indeed large meteors (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Histogram of events per year from the initial database

The majority of the data is available from 1850 onwards, so it has been decided to filter the database by specifically gathering 756 events recorded between the years 1807 and 2007, with their frequencies measured over

a sidereal year. The date does not correspond to the exact position of the Earth in its orbit, as the sidereal year does not have precisely 365 days. Additionally, the precession movement introduces a phase shift. To avoid errors caused by these two factors, the solar longitude has been taken as the measurement of ‘time’ for a year.

We analyzed this 200 year sample⁴, highlighting frequency peaks over 10 (this distinction is made because there is some baseline noise).

Figure 4 – Histogram of events per year from the initial database

Figure 5 – ‘KDE’ for the last 200 years UCM database, bandwidth adjusted by Silverman’s method * 0.15

In the ‘KDE’ plot (Figure 5), certain peaks that align with the histogram are accentuated, and we observe a peak on August 11-14, followed by several in November, possibly tied to meteor showers. However, in February, no intense meteor shower occurs.

2.2 Events characterization

Also, this database allows events to be categorized into sonic booms, damaging events and ordinary events.

⁴The second x-axis labels represent a year selected from the analyzed range in all the graphs

Events with a sonic boom

The entry of a bolide into the atmosphere results in a loss of mass, and the increasing hydrodynamic pressure causes the meteoroid to explode. These events are highly energetic due to their hypersonic velocities, surpassing the speed of sound in the air by a factor of 25, leading to the creation of sonic booms. Subsequently, the shockwave produced when exceeding the speed of sound is powerful enough to reach the surface, generating seismic waves. (Tapia & Trigo-Rodríguez, 2013) Both seismic and infrasound detection make it possible to detect daytime bolides.

Figure 6 – Histogram for events with a sonic boom during the last 200 years, UCM database

Events causing damage

The damage intensity depends on the speed and size, but when damage to buildings and glass breakage occurs, is due to the shockwave. (Rodríguez et al., 2013) Later, upon impact with the surface, an energy release of the order of a kiloton typically happens, comparable to atomic bombs, which leads to fires, craters, and earthquake-like vibrations.

Figure 7 – Histogram for events causing damage during the last 200 years, UCM database

As certain peaks continue to persist, they intensify, such as the ones in August and November (Figure 6) as well as in February (Figure 7).

3 No connection between meteor showers and events

The parameter used to measure the intensity of a meteor shower is ZHR, Zenithal Hourly Rate, which represents the maximum number of meteors an observer would see under perfect skies with a limiting magnitude of +6.5. When the meteor count per hour exceeds 10, it could be considered a significant meteor shower. (Rendtel, 2021)

The data for events with a frequency greater than 10 from Figure 4 and the possible meteor shower associated with the event with the day of maximum meteors per hour have been compiled into a table (Table 1). Some highlighted peaks do not have associated meteor showers with more than 10 ZHR, indicating that these are likely noise or unrelated events.

4 Comparing with a second sample, CNEOS database

4.1 Second sample description and analysis

This second database is a compilation of the brightest events that occurred between April 15, 1988, and April 4, 2023, totaling 953 data points as of the time of this analysis, with ongoing updates. It is maintained by NASA’s Center for Near-Earth Object Studies. The events are detected using instruments provided by the United States government, and, since 2019, some of them have been detected by instruments such as the Geostationary Lightning Mapper (GLM) on meteorological satellites like GOES⁵.

Figure 8 – Histogram for events during the last 35 years, CNEOS database

⁵<https://cneos.jpl.nasa.gov/fireballs/>

Month	Peak date	Frequency	Potential associated meteor shower	Maximum ZHR
February	05/02-08/02	10		
	11/02-14/02	10		
	20/02-23/02	12		
July	17/20 - 20/07	10		
August	02/08 - 08/08	11	Perseids	12/08 100
	11/08 - 14/08	14	Perseids	12/08 100
September	11/09 - 14/09	10		
October	06/10 - 09/10	11	Draconids	08/10 10
November	15/11 - 18/11	12	Leonids	17/11 10
	18/11 - 21/11	12	Leonids	17/11 10
	21/11- 24/11	10	Leonids	17/11 10
December	08/12 - 11/12	10	Geminids	14/12 150

Table 1 – Event dates occurring more than 10 times within the period from 1807 to 2007 that may be associated with meteor showers.

We spotted a peak during February 14 - February 17, when the Chelyabinsk event occurred, the most substantial event of the decade, releasing energy equivalent to 500 tons of TNT.

We conducted a KDE adjustment analogous to that of the first database with the same bandwidth, for a subsequent comparison between them. The result is a probability density function with the highest fluctuations occurring on the days of July 16, August 15, October 7 and February 18. In this case, the peaks are largely independent of meteor showers due to the instruments used for detection (Figure 9).

Figure 9 – KDE for the last 35 years CNEOS database, band- width adjusted by Silverman’s method * 0.15

4.2 Two samples comparison through the Bayes’ Theorem

Henceforth, we will proceed with the comparison of both samples using Bayes’ Theorem to multiply the probability density functions to relate their peaks.

Bayes’ Theorem is renowned for its significance in conditional probability and is expressed in the following formula:

$$P(H_i|data) = \frac{P(H_i)P(data|H_i)}{\sum_{k=1}^n P(data|H_k)P(H_k)}$$

In this equation, $P(data|H_i)$ represents the likelihood of the data concerning a hypothesis or event H_i , $P(H_i)$ is the initial or prior probability, and $P(H_i|data)$ is the final or posterior probability of H_i . The denominator serves as a normalization factor to ensure that the sum of all final probabilities equals one.

In our case, we will consider the prior information as the probability density function of the 200 years and the likelihood as the probability density function of the 35 years database. Combining the data from these two samples, we obtain the final probability density function, represented in the following graph with a green dashed line.

Figure 10 – Probability density functions of both databases and their combination using Bayes’ theorem

The recurring peaks, mainly independent of intense meteor showers, and the emergence of potential peaks that could be associated with these are presented. (Jenniskens, 1994)

5 Conclusions and additional remarks

The novel contribution of this study to the investigation of the frequency of these events is rooted in non-parametric and Bayesian statistics, utilizing the KDE method. Throughout the study, consistent peaks appear in both databases’ analysis, notably in the sonic boom data with a recurring February peak. This peak is

not associated with meteor showers due to the objects' size. Therefore, it can be concluded that if there is no regular meteor shower recorded but bolides are falling, it is not a random occurrence. New meteor showers might be occurring that we are unaware of, as these tend to vary over time, or they could be due to other physical phenomena.

The study has been completed by combining the two samples described throughout the work to create a probability density function from which more rigorous conclusions can be drawn, reducing biases present in these two samples. It is important to clarify that conducting statistics on these events is challenging, and all databases have biases. If one were to improve the results, additional databases that support or mitigate these biases could be incorporated and combined.

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